

Le Monde de l'Agriculture Régénérative

From this...

Counteracting Climate Change with Proven, Low-tech Solutions

**Centered on Natural Water Cycles
Vegetation, Herbivores, Living Soils, Agriculture, and People**

Sonoran Desert, Arizona

To this...

*Both CAUSE and VICTIM, but also
the source of the most powerful SOLUTIONS,
AGRICULTURE is at the very core of our climate crisis.*

Carbon rich sponges
are the substrate
of fertile soils,
bio-diversity,
water & food security
and Life on Earth.

Photo Pierre Masson

Ulrich Schreier

Le Monde de l'Agriculture Régénérative

Mai 2021 - updated June 2023

Elements to Fuel the Debate for a Climate-Smart World

The World's Water Cycle

Global Precipitation, Evaporation, Evapotranspiration and Runoff

Vapour transport

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Precipitation
458 000 km³

Vegetation is an excellent regulator of temperature, humidity, and climate. Everyone knows that in summer it is much hotter on city streets than in the countryside and a forest. Under the blazing sun, the bare ground dries out and degrades quickly, and temperatures on its surface can easily exceed 40, 50, or even 70 °C. These are conditions of desertification that are fatal for a good portion of our microbial friends, the engine, and the very basis of living soils, agriculture, Nature, and Life on Earth.

Thanks to shading and the cooling effect of **EVAPOTRANSPIRATION**, the plant's and the Planet's natural air-conditioning system, humidity is much higher and the temperature much lower under a green canopy. *Evapotranspiration, a key link between the small water cycle and climate regulation, is powered by Sunshine and Photosynthesis, Earth's free, carbon-negative, life-enhancing, sustainable Power Source.*

Apart from the strict temperature and humidity effect, vegetation also has a regulating effect on atmospheric CO₂, soil life and bio-fertility, water cycles, bio-diversity, weather, and local climates. The reforestation, permaculture, and regenerative grazing projects in dry-land areas presented in this document are examples of what can be achieved in a very short time and with modest resources. They also show that working in harmony with natural processes has not only ecological but also considerable economic and social benefits.

South Africa Holistic management on the left has brought back biodiversity and natural fertility by regenerating the soil, greening the desert, restoring water cycles and cooling the

Zimbabwe : Thanks to regenerative grazing, the vegetation comes back to life, the climate becomes more balanced and some creeks start flowing again.

Pakistan: Planting one billion trees to regenerate a 3,500 km² area in 5 years! Has now been extended to 2028 and 10 billion

India's Water Revolution : From Poverty to Permaculture

Born in 2016, it is already the biggest Permaculture venture on Earth! Its basis is sound water management and the enthusiastic support of a highly motivated population. Initiated by the [Paani Foundation](#), it has ***changed, in just 4 years***, the lives and prospects of some 4000 of Indias poorest villages!

Strong local support, reducing water loss thru runoff and keeping the rain falling during the Monsoon season inside the watershed, are the keys of the system. This is achieved through elaborate networks of harvesting, infiltration and storage of water, both underground and above ground, in order to cover the needs during the dry season.

[Andrew Millison's YouTube channel](#) has 2 videos of this project (India's Water Revolution **#1** and **#2**) and many others on permaculture projects in India and other parts of the World.

Organic Farming in the South of India

ZERO BUDGET NATURAL FARMING (ZBNF)

When we look at the improvements in the many "Man-Nature Co-Creation Projects" presented here, we are astonished by the relative ease and speed of the recoveries.

The situations shown in this document are based on the repair, the returning to wholeness, of damaged ecosystems through the restoration of green ground cover, biodiversity, water and weather cycles, and soil and plant functioning. Drawing on a wealth of data, knowledge, success stories, time-tested methods, and practical know-how, these initiatives have brought huge quantities of atmospheric carbon (CO₂) back into the soil, while producing ecological as well as economic and social benefits. All of this happened in a wide range of settings and in a surprisingly short time while getting by with relatively modest investments.

Both cause and victim of environmental degradation and climate change, humans and agriculture are also at the heart of the most effective, economical, and environmentally friendly **SOLUTIONS**. According to [Allan Savory](#), biologist, a pioneer in regenerating desertifying grasslands¹ and founder of the [Savory Institute](#), *agriculture in harmony with*

¹ In developing his holistic approach for regenerating grasslands by mimicking Nature using livestock, Alan Savory was strongly influenced by the work of the French chemist and agronomist [André Voisin \(1903-1964\)](#), known worldwide as the father of **rotational grazing** also referred to as regenerative or dynamic intensive grazing. Voisin is the author of many publications and books on grazing, animal husbandry, and health, the most notable being *Grass Productivity (1957)* and *Soil, Grass, and Cancer (1959)*. Both have been widely translated and continue to be key references in the field.

Rotational grazing is not only sustainable but also much more productive (higher stocking rates) than continuous grazing.

*natural processes is **our only option** for restoring natural water cycles, re-greening large desertifying areas, reversing global warming and fighting poverty, malnutrition, social and political unrest in many of the world's poorest regions?*

The Institute is on a mission to regenerate desertifying grasslands and the livelihoods of their inhabitants, through regenerative agriculture with properly managed pastures and livestock (holistic management). The institute has organized a worldwide movement of farmers and land managers whose hubs are present on all five continents. Also known as Savory Global, its network covers more than 13 million hectares, (130 000 km²), over four times the size of Belgium, making major contributions toward grassland rehabilitation, biodiversity, and the restoration of local water and weather cycles. Their work has major impacts on mitigating and reversing global warming, carbon sequestration, and the production of healthy foods and drinking water. In addition, it produces a precious knowledge base as well as big economic and social rewards for farmers, ranchers, and local communities.

² Given the enormous inertia of our modern world and the difficulty of curbing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in the short run, even under the most **optimistic scenarios**, agriculture seems to be the only credible way to rapidly mitigate and reverse global warming, substantially increase green cover over large areas and economically and sustainably reduce CO₂ levels in the atmosphere!

The many successful examples from [Savory Global](#), Brazil, India, China, Pakistan, and many other countries show that the restoration of Nature, soils, and water cycles does not require huge investments compared to some of the high-tech mega-projects that keep making most of the headlines. Using neither synthetic fertilizers, pesticides, nor the controversial techniques of geo-engineering and GMOs, they employ hardly any fossil fuels or other scarce resources. Combined with properly managed livestock and crop production, they can provide large economic, ecological, and social benefits in just a few years, sometimes showing significant improvements as soon as the first season (see e.g. India's Water Revolution on page 3). A crucial source of soil fertility and food security, these low-tech solutions allow for an immediate start of thousands of decentralized and autonomous projects all around the Globe, without needing huge amounts of capital or complex organizational structures. Producing surprisingly fast and easily measurable results, they are affordable, low-tech, low-input, and low-energy, but high on people, economic, social, and environmental benefits.

Such prospects are a long shot from the highly technical and costly proposals focusing on CO₂ (e.g. [CCS technology](#)). Although still at an experimental stage and an uncertain future, these proposals are already dominating headlines in international climate conferences, scientific publications, and the media. Given the fact that the sun, plants, and photosynthesis are the Planet's all-in-one, carbon-absorbing, sustainable power source, and air conditioning system, **it appears doubtful that merely lowering atmospheric CO₂ levels with technological means, if at all economically feasible, would reverse global warming all by itself³.**

Given the extent of deserts and desertifying areas located for the most part in the poorest regions of the Planet, the potential for restoring soils, vegetation and water cycles is enormous. Producing food and drinking water in quantity and quality, the deployment of **EFFECTIVE SOLUTIONS** is crucial not only in terms of climate change, but also from an **economic, ecological and social** perspective.

³ A multitude of recent climate models and projections make the situation highly opaque and confusing. Based on mechanistic and linear reasoning, they are full of unknowns, contradictions and regularly changing assumptions. We are far from the common sense and transparency of water based bio-inclusive climate models and the resulting greening solutions - Even if it were possible to bring down CO₂ levels with technology, it is doubtful that it would make a dent into Global Warming, let alone reverse it, without living soils, vegetation, herbivores and naturally functioning bio-systems.

The **success of the many re-greening projects** in desertifying dry-land areas based on restoring water⁴ cycles and damaged ecosystems confirms the value of bio-inclusive climate models centered on water, living soils, vegetation, herbivores⁵, and agriculture.

Re-Greening Deserts is Possible!

Lessons from the China Loess Plateau

John D Liu, cameraman and ecologist, has documented since 1995 **the greening of the Loess Plateau** in China as well as many other Greening Projects around the Planet showing simple, affordable, low-tech, solutions to restore heavily degraded ecosystems in a surprisingly short time.

By degrading soil and environment, over-exploitation has turned this once fertile area into a desert.

While the Great Green Wall is advancing ...

... food and water shortages, poverty and social tensions are receding!

Source: The Environmental Media Project & John D. Liu

The Loess Plateau through the glasses of Wikipedia

Loess Plateau Watershed Rehabilitation Project, China

Between 1994 and 2009 about 35,000 square kilometers, about 5% of the total area, have been restored.

“The lessons from the Loess Plateau show that it is possible to restore large scale damaged ecosystems and that this mitigates climate impacts, makes land more resilient and increases productivity.”

- John D. Liu

This was the cradle and food basket of ancient Chinese civilizations - the Garden of Eden of the Orient.

Achievements: it took 2.5 million people out of poverty - Small dams reduce flooding and provide water to villagers - Reduced erosion and sediment flow to the Yellow River - **Beneficial effects on climate**. As in the case of "India's Water Revolution", the key ingredients of this project are also sound water, agricultural and environmental management, combined with a strong community involvement!

Update February 2021: [How Is China Turning Deserts Into Arable Lands?](#)

⁴ Water's average atmospheric vapor concentration is about 25 000 ppmv or ~60x higher than CO₂ and has a 2 to 3x higher GHG effect. Regarding its physicochemical, biological, and calorific behavior, it is one of the strangest substances there is. - For a growing number of climatologists, it is not CO₂ and GHGs but natural phenomena and massive soil and biosphere destruction that cause global and local warming. Since the biosphere and water in its many forms, locations, and cycles (snow, ice, liquid, vapor, haze, clouds, soil moisture, plant sap,...), are key factors in climate regulation, **their rapid restoration is crucial, to get us out of the climate dilemma**

⁵ Although it may be surprising that many restoration projects include livestock, let's not forget that **herbivores, especially cattle and huge grassland roaming buffalo herds**, have been a key factor for the stability of grassland-based bio-systems of which they are an integral part. In addition, they are an important source of food and soil fertility! It is important to realize, that the problem is not livestock in itself, but it's poor management by humans.

Validating the pivotal role of agriculture and people in this vital process, these results are ground for plenty of optimism even when it comes to large-scale *greening projects in some of the driest and most inhospitable places on Earth*. With a highly favorable cost-benefit ratio and beneficial impact on the local climate and communities, these endeavors will be all the more effective if, at the same time, we reduce GHG emissions, over-exploitation of natural resources, waste, pollution, soil artificialisation, deforestation and degradation of agricultural land by over-grazing, deep plowing, bare ground, synthetic fertilizers, pesticides, antibiotics, and other destructive practices. The list is long, very long!

Greening some of the driest deserts on Earth

Geoff Lawton is with Bill Mollison one of the permaculture pioneers: **Discovering an Oasis in the American Desert**

Once man had primed the pump, Nature took care of the maintenance for 80 years, while the surrounding desert remained as dry and desolate as before!

The Al Baydha permaculture project in the Saudi Arabian desert - Video

Harvesting rain : the rain that falls locally to "prime the pump" for building living soils, biodiversity, biomass and accumulate stable organic matter has been the basis for regenerating some of the driest, hottest and most desolate places on the Planet.

Greening the Desert in the Dead Sea Valley

10-year timeline

Started in 2007 but hampered by endless violence and wars, this crucial initiative to slow desertification and stop the Sahel from moving north, *is of prime importance not only for Africa and Europe, but for the climate of the whole planet!* - [FAO article](#)

Virtuous feedback loops⁶: by stopping water loss through runoff and the gradual improvement of rainfall patterns, soil life, and vegetation are generating a virtuous spiral that takes CO₂ from the atmosphere and turns it into organic compounds, bio-fertility and a diversified community of living organisms in the soil. Above ground as vegetation and its dying residues. By its capacity to sequester large amounts of carbon⁷, recycle water, and nutrients, and metabolize toxins, AGRICULTURE, by far humanity's most important economic and social endeavor, is at the heart of this virtuous loop. With a low energy footprint, to the extent it is guided by agro-ecological principles, it can do without all, or at least most chemical fertilizers and pesticides. Regenerative farming practices along these lines have a *beneficial effect not only on climate and environment but also on crop health, weed pressure, plant resilience against pests, and climate hazards. In addition, they have a big impact on farm productivity, profitability, and sustainability, on food quality, safety, and security, on health, job creation, and the economic and social development of rural areas.*

⁶ **Walter Jehne**, an Australian Soil and Climate Scientist proposes a convincing **Climate Model**. By putting water cycles, spongy soil aggregates and vegetation in the center, he explains not only the **WHYs, the HOWs and rationales** behind the virtuous feedback loop, but, in proposing proven solutions, has a **very optimistic message for us.** - [Climate Model](#)

⁷ According to a **publication** by **Dr. Rattan Lal**, a world renowned soil scientist, the potential for CO₂ sequestration in the biosphere is estimated at 157 ppm over the next 80 years. *This, by 2100, would bring CO₂ levels in the atmosphere back to pre-industrial levels of about 260 ppm.* Judging from these estimates, *the C storage capacity of the world's soils and biosphere is huge.* Unlike industrial feedlot and indoor livestock operations that emit large amounts of greenhouse gases (GHGs), holistic animal husbandry integrating crop production is not only sustainable but it is also more productive and has a favorable carbon balance - less carbon in the air, more in the biosphere (see White Oaks Pastures on page 31).

The common threads in all of the successful initiatives highlighted in this document have been a passionate group of visionaries, competent pioneers, and leaders associated with the direct involvement and enthusiastic support of the various stakeholders, most of all the disadvantaged populations in poor areas who have seen rapid improvements in their livelihoods.

The particularly effective rehabilitation projects, both from a climate aspect and from the point of view of their economic, social and political impact, are the ones in poverty-stricken dry-land regions of Africa, India, Pakistan, China, and Asian grasslands. Having accumulated precious know-how and sometimes enjoying organizational and financial support at the government level, most of these "Man-Nature Co-Creation Projects" could be scaled in a very short time and produce, within just a decade or two, major impacts on Global Warming, while reducing food and water scarcity, as well as healing many of the Blue Planets damaged landscapes and ecosystems.⁸

⁸ To stop violence and wars, and establish peace and political stability in these regions, while slowing migration to big cities and industrialized countries, economic development, job creation, quality food and water in sufficient quantities are crucial! According to a growing number of scientists, consultants and practitioners, the best way to get there is in conjunction with regenerative practices such as permaculture, regenerative agriculture, tree-planting and well managed livestock. Animals have been precious friends and our traveling companions since the dawn of times. They have always played a key role in our lives and in agriculture, for the good and for the bad. For the good, as wild herds of herbivores and their predators roaming the grasslands or as well managed livestock. For the bad, if they are poorly managed by humans, a problem which unfortunately has been more often the rule than the exception and has accompanied the downfall of most past civilisations. The end phase was often uncontrolled grazing of sheep and goats which gave many eco-systems the final blow!

Partnering with Nature to reverse Global Warming by restoring water cycles and damaged ecosystems.

Reason for plenty of optimism: we know the causes and have the solutions to mitigate climate change and reverse global warming. By implementing thousands of greening ventures all around the Planet through soil and environmental restoration with the type of methodology described in this document, we can turn the tide within a few years. The many pioneering success stories show us that it can be done and also how we can do it. In some cases like the **Indian initiative "From Poverty to Permaculture"** with its "Water Cup Competition" and strong community involvement, the first significant benefits of this grassroots tsunami came as soon as the first season! Being a highly motivating enterprise, **ecosystem restoration will provide new optimism and meaningful jobs for millions of people, in particular youngsters looking for meaningful jobs.**

People and agriculture are the corner stone : Regenerative Agriculture, Permaculture and various other agro-ecological systems propose effective **SOLUTIONS** for restoring soil life, bio-diversity, humus (organic C), bio-fertility and hydrological cycles. By reducing, in most cases eliminating agrochemical inputs all together, these avenues open doors for moving rapidly towards productive and sustainable eco-systems without drowning in a jungle of weeds or suffering from poor yields and food shortages. **Being synergistic, crop production and animal husbandry should be integrated wherever possible to reach optimum soil regeneration, productivity and sustainability.**

What if the most destitute regions in the world and their impoverished populations were first in line to save our Planet from overheating? Given the size, location and diversity of these dry-land areas, the majority being grasslands, their impact on climate change can be huge and very likely a determining factor, if not **THE dominating factor**, for winning our race against global warming! Isn't that a compelling reason for the rich industrialized countries of the North to join and strongly support, financially and otherwise, the poor countries of the South? Such a cooperation wouldn't only change the climate, but has the potential to change the World.

We have the understanding, the knowledge, the know-how, the blue prints to follow, and the resources to repair in a short time, what took us and our ancestors several millennia to ruin.

Our toolbox is overflowing with proven solutions!

Bibliography

John D. Liu

<https://knav.academia.edu/JohnDLiu>

The problem of climate change is more complex than we think, but, as more and more greening initiatives are showing, it could be easier, faster and cheaper to solve than we imagine, ... if we take a fresh look at its causes and solutions.

Jean-Marc Jancovici

[What is a climate model? What are the models' first conclusions? - models with CO2 as primary warming criteria.](#)

Kravčík, Pokorný, Kohutiar, Kováč, Tóth

[Kravčík_&_al-Water for the Recovery of the Climate - A New Water Paradigm](#)

Machmuller 2015, Rowntree 2016, Stanley 2018, Teague 2018

[Four publications on carbon sequestration](#)

Markus Dotterweich

[Dotterweich-The history of human-induced soil erosion](#)

Rattan Lal

[Rattan-Managing soils for negative feedback to climate change](#)

Walter Jehne

Interview: [Supporting the Soil Carbon Sponge](#)

Video conference: [Jehne-Climate Solutions for a Blue Planet](#)

[Restoring water cycles to naturally cool climates and reverse global warming](#)

Ulrich Schreier

[Articles on climat](#)

[Le Monde de l'Agriculture régénérative - Articles divers](#)

Having made no progress in slowing Global Warming and reducing Extreme Weather Events by following CO₂, GHG, high-tech, mega-project, big-ticket based thinking, we urgently need **New Ideas, a New Vision!**

A partial overview of organizations engaged in large-scale ecosystem restoration

- Bonn Challenge (350 Million Hectares by 2030): <https://www.bonnchallenge.org/>
- Brazilian Forest Restoration (Sebastiao & Leila Salgado): [2 million trees in 20 years](#)
- Caledonian Forest restoration: <https://alanwatsonfeatherstone.com/restoring-the-caledonian-forest/>
- China Loess Plateau Restoration: [2016 publication by John Liu and Bradley Hiller.](#)
- Commonland: <https://www.commonland.com/>
- Ecosystem Restoration Camps: <https://ecosystemrestorationcamps.org/>
- Forest Man of India: [Jadav Payeng](#)
- Great Green Wall of Africa: <https://www.greatgreenwall.org/>
- Mexican Initiative 20x20: [Restoring 1 Million Hectares of Degraded Land](#)
- Paani Foundation (India's Water Revolution): <https://www.paanifoundation.in/>
- Pakistan, Ten billion tree tsunami: <http://tbhttp.gov.pk/about-tbhttp/>
- Savory Institute, Facilitating the regeneration of Grasslands: <https://savory.global/>
- SEKEM - Sustainable Development since 1977: www.sekem.com
- UN Environment Programme (UNEP): [The world's biggest ecosystem restoration project](#)
- SER (Society for Ecological Restoration): Ecosystem Restoration Directory: <https://www.ser-rc.org/directory/>

All really important innovations and changes normally start from tiny minorities of people who do use their creative freedom."

Ernst F. Schumacher
Economist and author of
"Small is Beautiful"

and Fonder of the *Appropriate Technology Movement*

No problem can be solved from the same level of consciousness that created it.

Albert Einstein

The problem of global warming is more complex than we think, but may be easier, faster and cheaper to solve than we imagine!

Mai 2021- updated June 2023

Ulrich Schreier F-49370 Vernoux

Appendix A - The proof is in the Pudding

BEFORE

NW China's Mu Us Desert
42,200 km²

« The difference between a Garden and a Desert is not Water, it's Man »
Touareg Proverb

0:52 PREVIEW

AFTER

↑ CO₂ ↑ H₂O ↑ °C ↓ CO₂ ↓ H₂O ↓ °C

BEFORE RESTORATION

Restoration in Ethiopia
10,000 km²

AFTER RESTORATION

2008

2009

2010

2011

Photo sequence showing mangrove restoration at Palk Bay, India. (OMCAR Foundation)

3:40

Restoring a 2000 ha Farm in Texas

2006

2013

Australia

Source: Mulloon Institute

Restoration at the Mulloon Creek Natural Farms

2006

2013

Australia

Mulloon Institute
For environment, farming and society.

Restoration at the Mulloon Creek Natural Farms

1971

Rock Dhu at Norville Family Farm

2013

Australia

Australia

2009

Yanet Creek Rehydration Project

2016

Australia

Winona - A case study in resilience

SoilsforLife

Garry Kadwell's Fairhalt

Case Studies

Salisbury: Rehabilitating the Scalds

Winona - Pasture Cropping the Way to Health

Mulloon Creek Catchment

'Dukes Plain'- Continuous Improvement of the Farm Resource

'Shannon Vale Station'- Weed control without herbicide is not a load of bull

Olsen's Hallora

Appendix B - Facts and New Insights into Climate Change

What everybody knows about weather and climate

On a hot summer day it is much cooler in a lush forest than on concrete, treeless city streets.

And

- It is cooler after a thunderstorm than before.
- During the day a cloud cover keeps the mercury down.
- At night it is the opposite, it stays warmer under a cloud cover.
- The temperature difference between day and night is usually much larger during dry weather periods without cloud cover than during rainy periods with permanent cloud cover.
- In a cloudless desert where the humidity is very low, the temperature differences between day and night are huge.
- Bare soil is much hotter than soil under standing grass or trees.

These differences are due to the **WATER** and its natural cycles.

Both CAUSE and VICTIM, but also the source of the most POWERFUL SOLUTIONS, AGRICULTURE is at the very core of our climate and environmental crisis

$$C_{sol} + C_{veg} \approx 4 \times C_{atm}$$

In addition to the 1580 GT shown in this diagram, the soil also contains about 750 GT of C in various mineral forms, mostly as carbonates ($CaCO_3$, $MgCO_3$).

Vegetation and soil organic matter are two expandable reservoirs that agriculture can rapidly enlarge by increasing plant cover and improving water and soil management (increase biodiversity, soil health and humus levels!

In addition to the carbon deficit in the biosphere, Planet Earth suffers from a thermal imbalance. According to the International Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), our Globe receives on average 342 watts of solar radiation per square meter (W/m^2). But because because of damaged ecosystems and the Natural Water Cycles with its lower cloud related albedo effect, only 339 W/m^2 are emitted back. The differential of $-3 W/m^2$ or about -1% is what heats up the Planet. The fastest, most effective and cheapest way to reduce this imbalance is by increasing plant cover and soil organic matter.

WATER CYCLES and AGRICULTURE, our prime levers for climate control

Much of their different abundance as well as the different dynamic and physicochemical behavior of water (H₂O) and CO₂ in the atmosphere, the soil, oceans⁹, freshwater reservoirs, and life processes, point toward the water as the dominant factor in climate regulation. On average there are 60 times (up to ~120x) more water in the atmosphere than CO₂ (~25 000 versus 400 ppmv or 20 versus 0,8g/m³ with a respective specific heat of 2,1 versus 0,8 J/g). Multiplying weight (g) by specific heat (J) gives water a calorific edge of 65 to 1. Regarding the overall infrared greenhouse effect, water is again dominating by about 75 to 25%. The imbalance is even more lopsided concerning their average atmospheric residence time which is 8 to 10 days for the "liquid gold" versus 100 to 300 years for CO₂. When it comes to physicochemical properties and reactivity, the differences are again huge. Between -60 and +60 °C, CO₂ is a relatively inert, odorless, and colorless gas often dissolved in a liquid or a solid, in many instances water. Water on the other hand is the strangest and by far the most abundant substance on the surface of the Earth. Covering about 70% of the Blue Planet, it would form a 3000 m thick layer if it were spread out evenly over the entire globe. Always present where we find life, water is chemically highly reactive. It fills untold numbers of functions and takes on many different forms, some highly transparent with a blueish tint, others opaque: snow, ice, liquid, vapor, haze, clouds {Earth cooling albedo effect}, soil moisture, dew, plant sap, hydration layers, clusters, etc.).

This short comparison between these two inseparable partners for life on Earth points strongly toward water's dominant role when it comes to climate regulation. This fact sends us a very optimistic message and gives us many powerful levers to overcome Global Warming, endemic fresh-water shortages, and extreme weather events by repairing the Planet's damaged ecosystems and hydrology. This is achieved by good water management and through increased plant coverage, biodiversity, soil fertility, humus levels (carbon and water-rich sponges), and biomass production, all of which have a positive effect not only on water cycles and climate but also on fresh-water and food security.

Water controls the Planet's heat dynamics and climate !

Facts that tell a climate story	Water (H ₂ O)	CO ₂
Atmospheric abundance in volume (ppmv)	~25000	~400 (ratio ~1:60)
Density at 25 °C (g/l)	0,8	1,9
Heat capacity of gas at 25 °C (cal/g)	0,5	0,2
Ratio of atmospheric heat content	~60	1
Phases in the range of -50 to +50 °C	Ice, Liquid, Gas, aerosol	Only gas phase
Phase changes are energy intensive (cal/g)	80 to melt, 540 liquid to gas	None
Green house effect (%)	~75	~25
Albedo cooling effect	High & crucial to temp control	None
Chemical reactivity	high (acido-basic, redox)	low (~inert)
Time in atmosphere (velocity-exchange)	8 to 12 days	~5 years

⁹ Containing about 50 times more CO₂ than the atmosphere, oceans act as huge buffers for many parameters including temperature. This means that the effect of any remedial climate action will be much slower on the Planet's oceans than on its water cycles and weather. Being constantly replenished from ocean reservoirs, atmospheric CO₂ will continue to have a positive influence on plant growth for quite some time.

Since 1970, the increase in temperature and climatic accidents has accelerated. Although we have passed a critical milestone, progress and prospects in the right direction are few and far between. We remain obsessed with GHGs, CO₂, various band-aids and financial tools such as carbon certificates, the financialization of water consumption, subsidies and tax credits, instead of moving towards proven initiatives such as the restoration of damaged ecosystems and natural water cycles.

-> <https://cutt.ly/r3cmRFr>

By increasing the Planet's green cover it is possible to compensate during the summer of the northern hemisphere, the natural increase of CO₂ during the winter

"Since water controls more than 95% of our planet's heat dynamics, our focus should be on water and the restoration of its cycles, not on CO₂ emissions!" - WJ

CO₂ helps increase plant cover and lower temperatures!

Assimilated via photosynthesis, the **CO₂ carbon is the main food for plants** who "eat" CO₂ and water (H₂O) to produce oxygen (O₂) and carbohydrates (C_xH_yO_z) which are the basic ingredients of life on Earth. Vegetable growers use this well known phenomenon to increase yields by enriching their greenhouse air with CO₂.

According to the work of different groups of scientists whose results have been published in peer reviewed journals, this same process of plant stimulation operates at the planetary level and, with the **increase in atmospheric CO₂, has led to an increase in plant cover**. This greening phenomenon, measured by the greening index, can be clearly seen on satellite images, and in turn leads to a drop in temperature and thus a cooling effect on the climate in several regions.

The **positive feedback loop of CO₂ increase on plant growth** and climate is the result of increased photosynthesis, plant growth, and evapotranspiration, three key links in the natural water and rain cycles. Since this positive effect goes far beyond the negative side of the greenhouse effect, **the increase of atmospheric CO₂ has an overall beneficial effect on greening and in turn on temperatures**

nature reviews
earth & environment

CO₂ -> greening

Characteristics, drivers and feedbacks of global greening

Shilong Piao, Xuhui Wang, Taejin Park, Chi Chen, Xu Lian, Yue He, Jarle W. Bjerke, Anping Chen, Philippe Ciais, Hans Tammervik, Ramakrishna R. Nemani & Ranga B. Myneni
Nature Reviews Earth & Environment 1, 14–27(2020)

2000–2018 (MODIS)

More and more scientific publications challenge the CO₂ dogma!

Plants love CO₂, because CO₂ is their food!

https://twitter.com/Elojis_F/

Atmospheric Temperature and CO₂: Hen-or-Egg Causality?

by Demetris Koutsoyiannis^{1,*} and Zbigniew W. Kundzewicz²

Sci 2020, 2(3), 72; <https://doi.org/10.3390/sci2030072>

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/346356891_Atmospheric_Temperature_and_CO2_Hen-Or-Egg_Causality

We examine the relationship of global temperature and atmospheric carbon dioxide concentration using the most reliable global data that are available—the data gathered from several sources, covering the common time interval 1980–2019, available at the monthly time step.

The results of the study support the hypothesis that both causality directions exist, with $T \rightarrow CO_2$ being the dominant, despite the fact that the former $CO_2 \rightarrow T$ prevails in public, as well as in scientific, perception. Indeed, our results show that changes in CO₂ follow changes in T by about six months on a monthly scale, or about one year on an annual scale.

For the monthly scale the attained p-values in the direction $T \rightarrow [CO_2]$ are always smaller than in direction $[CO_2] \rightarrow T$ by about 4 to 5 orders of magnitude, thus clearly supporting $T \rightarrow [CO_2]$ as dominant direction.

file:///Users/ulrichschreier/Downloads/121106HumInmetaPhaseRelationCO2andTemp.pdf

Global and Planetary Change
Volume 100, January 2013, Pages 51–69

The phase relation between atmospheric carbon dioxide and global temperature

Cite Humlum, H., Kjell Stordahl, Jan-Erik Solheim

Fig. 3. 12-month change of global atmospheric CO₂ concentration (NOAA; green), global sea surface temperature (HadSST2; blue) and global surface air temperature (GISS; red dotted). All graphs are showing monthly values of DIFF12, the difference between the average of the last 12 months and the average for the previous 12 months for each data series.

Temperature Leads

T → CO₂

Many recent publications show that CO₂ follows temperature (T) by about 6 months on a monthly basis, or by about a year on an annual basis.

Walter Jehne and his **Bio-inclusive ABCD climate model** put water, spongy soil aggregates and vegetation in the center. Dealing with the multidimensional nature of climate, incorporating the biology, the chemistry and the physics, Jehne elucidates many phenomena that are difficult to explain: "why water and not CO₂ and GHGs is the key", "Asian brown haze with 4% moisture, 90% relative humidity plus pollutant smog", "diminishing of Earth's **albedo** which increases global warming", "high-pressure heat domes over bare, dry areas", "humid aridifying drought", the role of agriculture in eco-system destruction and desertification now and by our ancestors", or California's drought and fire crisis which, without appropriate action, may lead to desertification and the collapse of its huge agricultural complex.

Agriculture

Maximum plant growth for maximum carbohydrate production via sun, green plants and photosynthesis. Biodiversity - 365 days/year

Burn by fire or oxidation:

-> CO₂ from slash and burn, cultivation, bare soils, fallow, compaction, irrigation, chemical fertilizers, pesticides.
-> **Global Warming**

Three of Jehne's statements:

"For the last 4 billion years the climate of the Blue Planet has been controlled by hydrological processes. **Over 90% of the global heat dynamics and balance is governed by a range of water-based processes.**"

"Restoring natural processes via the regeneration of our landscapes is now critical in order to restore the former levels of high albedo clouds that naturally helped cool the planet."

"Water accounts for about 80%, CO₂ for 20% of the greenhouse effect,"

Dividends from the C sponge:

Water/nutrient availability
Microbial cycles, Root domin.
Pest/drought resistance,
Autonomy/very low input
Productivity resilience (+yields)

Carbon: microbial digestion

-> stable soil carbon sponges.
Raw materials: roots (40%), exudates (40%), litter (20%)
-> Humates and glomalin,
-> **Regeneration**

Feeding and *keeping our "team" of soil microorganismes happy* is the the basis. According to Jehne, we have all it takes for greening the Planet and reversing desertification and Global Warming: the understanding, the know-how, the resources and the pioneers showing the way. The outcome is in our hands and depends on how we tilt the carbon balance in favor of **C** and away from **B**. This balance is very poor, and usually negative, with conventional farming, but can reach 60 to 70% of the produced biomass as stable soil carbon sponges, in regenerative systems with sound water, soil, biomass and microbial management. **Jehne Climate Model**

"Climate change will persist until we heal the Planet's water cycles!"

Herbivores and the Planet's Grasslands are key to Climate Control!

SUN The strongest force in our solar system, the sun creates plant growth through photosynthesis	RAIN Rainfall infiltrates soil and allows grass to grow. Thriving grasslands are effective at recharging aquifers.	PROPER GRAZING Managed grazing stimulates further grass growth and root development	RUMINANT ANIMAL Grass is digested in the rumen and converted to muscle	BIO DIVERSITY Thriving grasslands provide habitat to thousands of living organisms
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Herbivores belong to Grassland, like Grass to Soil Fertility and Plants to the Planet!

This treasure has been decimated and turned into CO₂, while disturbing Earth's water cycles, grasslands and climate!

THRIVING GRASSLANDS Grasses capture CO ₂ from the atmosphere more effectively than any other functioning earth system	GRASS ROOTS Grass roots cycle carbon deep into the soil, thereby combating climate change	SOIL CARBON in the ground- Soil carbon increases the pastures ability to hold water and feeds soil biology	SOIL BIOLOGY feeds plants and grasses while improving the nutritional value of food	HOOVES aerate soil, break up compacted earth, and improve circulation	URINE AND MANURE fertilizes soil through animal compost and feeds desirable biology
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<https://savory.global/resource-library/>

IT'S NOT THE COW, IT'S THE HOW

@SUSTAINABLEDISH | SACREDCOW.INFO

CONTINUOUS GRAZING	MANAGED GRAZING
<p>Constant access to entire pasture, leading to overgrazing</p>	<p>Access to smaller pastures, adaptive based on changing conditions</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Less wildlife habitat More exposed soil Reduced forage diversity Increased rainfall runoff Less healthy animals More parasites 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Better wildlife habitat More microbial diversity Increased rainfall absorption More carbon sequestration Healthier animals Fewer parasites

SACREDCOW

METHANE CLAIMS AGAINST CATTLE ARE OVERBLOWN

@SUSTAINABLEDISH | SACREDCOW.INFO

According to the EPA, all livestock only represents 3.9% of the US GHG emissions, which is far lower than the 18% - 51% range many plant-based advocates report. The largest source of GHG emissions in the US comes from energy and transportation.

2016 US Total GHG Emissions Source: US EPA

Transportation	Electricity generation	Industry	Commercial	Residential	Ag-Crops	Ag-Livestock	Ag-Puels	U.S. territories
28.5%	28.4%	21.6%	6.4%	5%	4.7%	3.9%	0.8%	0.7%

Within the livestock category, beef represents 2% of total US GHG emissions.

1. <https://www.epa.gov/greenhouse-gases/ghg-emissions-agriculture>

SACREDCOW

CATTLE CARBON CYCLING VS. FOSSIL FUELS

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FOSSIL FUELS

Recent carbon is directly added to the atmosphere as CO₂

THE COW'S CARBON CYCLE

All the carbon in the cow, its feed and its feedlot, comes from the air it took through the grass that the cow ate.

CARBON SEQUESTRATION

With the help of grazing animals, carbon is taken from the air by plants & stored into the soil providing energy for soil microbes to build healthy & diverse systems.

UP TO 400% MORE CARBON STORED IN SOIL

UP TO 40% LESS CO₂ RELEASED

UP TO 10% MORE NUTRIENT DENSITY

UP TO 10% MORE WATER CAPACITY

UP TO 10% MORE RESILIENCE

UP TO 10% MORE PRODUCTIVITY

UP TO 10% MORE PROFITABILITY

UP TO 10% MORE SUSTAINABILITY

UP TO 10% MORE RESILIENCE

UP TO 10% MORE PRODUCTIVITY

UP TO 10% MORE PROFITABILITY

UP TO 10% MORE SUSTAINABILITY

SACREDCOW

Perennial grassland plants and their root systems

Deep-rooted perennial plants are a key element to re-green the Planet's grassland regions.

The World's natural grasslands are the result of a symbiosis over millennia between deep-rooted perennial plants and wildlife, in particular huge herds of herbivores and their predators who were an essential part of this sustainable ecosystem.

Source: Conservation Research Institute - <https://www.cri.org/files/wordpress.com/2017/08/ncgpp5-6-11x-7.pdf>

Dr. Jerry Glover
USAID

Wheat-grass perennial wheat
Rooting 2.5 to 3 m

Entanglement of Indian grass, Compass plant, Big bluestem grass
Rooting 3 to 4 m

Missouri Goldenrod

Dr Glover's work with perennial plants shows the importance of this treasure man has plunde-

Repairing the water cycle is conceptually simple & affordable...

Simple repairs...

- Conserve rainwater which falls to the ground to rebuild aquifers and stop accelerated run-off.
- Preserve surface water so it either *infiltrates soil*, or evaporates locally.
- Use greening to enhance water retention and lower air temperatures.
- Reduce erosion to increase the watershed's carrying capacity and save soil.
- Don't drain low-lying land, especially floodplains and mangroves.

... Affordable

- Scientists estimate that 0.1% of GDP p.a. over 10-15 years must be invested in water and soil conservation, plus revised agricultural practices.
- However, to be effective almost every country will need to participate: global weather stability returns only when adjacent small water cycles are repaired.
- **Poorer countries will require financial aid. Unless local peoples commit to the entire process, failure is the likely result: *Education is vital.***

Kravec et

We are all in this together

PHOTOSYNTHESIS

CELLULAR RESPIRATION

CELLULAR RESPIRATION

shutterstock.com · 753253606

These two processes are polar opposites

- Plants via CO₂ and photosynthesis produce our food and our oxygen

- Humans and animals through respiration produce plant "food" (CO₂)

The ☀️ is the energy source for all life on Earth.

Nom du gaz	% présent
Diazote (N ₂)	78 %
Dioxygène (O ₂)	21 %
Argon (Ar)	0,93 %
Water vapor (H ₂ O)	0 - 4 %
Gaz carbonique (CO ₂)	0,043 %

The problem of climate change is more complex than we think, but, as more and more re-greening initiatives are showing, is easier, faster and cheaper to solve than we imagine!

Appendix C

Historical perspective of soil and environmental degradation

Critias: «Soil has been carried to the bottom of the sea.. Earthy high mountains, that in the past carried tall forest and large pastures, have become rocky lands and look like the bones of a sick body... In the past rain water was utilized and did not run on the barren land to the sea as it does now. It infiltrated and stored into the soil and it was distributed in springs, fountains and river streams .«

Plato (427-347 BCE)

- Bare soil,**
-> **Desertification**
-> **Drought**
-> **Flooding,**
-> **Erosion,**
-> **Gullying,**
-> **Desolation!**

At this stage of ecosystem breakdown,
Nature Needs Man as Partner and Co-Creator
to heal its sick body!

Desertification - Rehabilitation

Water sinks in, the soil heals and stabilizes!
Rainfall increases and the climate becomes more moderate.
The land recovers, becomes productive and hospitable.

Man-made desertification, especially in the Mediterranean Basin, has been widespread in ancient times and was accurately described by contemporaries such as Plato.

(Picture S. Leu, Judean Mountains, 30 km from Hura)

Soil and environmental destruction by man is not new and began at least 10 thousand years ago when our ancestors became sedentary and started to farm. In the past their main "weapons" were fire, axe, hoe and livestock, the first two mainly for preparing food, heating, clearing forests and producing raw materials for building houses and making various objects, the hoe, later joined by the plow, and livestock mainly for working the soil and producing food. Both deforestation and agriculture were practiced close to the settlements and only affected the surrounding environment. After the collapse of a civilization which, at the time, covered only a small part of the globe, Nature generally managed to erase its traces in areas with sufficient rainfall, whereas the wounds remained wide open in the more arid and more populated regions such as the Middle East (Mesopotamia with its proverbial Garden of Eden), around parts of the Mediterranean and the Huangtu Loess Plateau in China.

If soil and environmental destruction was more localized and took a few centuries or millennia in ancient times, it has become a global problem today and takes just a few years or decades, since many more of us are living on the Blue Planet and we now occupy large parts of its terrestrial landmass. Other factors that help explain the accelerated degradation of landscapes are rampant urbanism and sprawling infrastructures, waste, highly mechanized agricultural systems with oversized and over-powered equipment, intensive tillage, overgrazing, factory farms and feed lots, toxic side effects of synthetic fertilizers, pesticides, antibiotics, hormones, etc.

Today, we have detailed knowledge of the **WHYs** and the **HOWs** of desertification, and **PROVEN SOLUTIONS** to stop and reverse it!

Man walked across the Planet and left a desert in his footsteps

What happened to the Garden of Eden, the fertile crescent of the Middle East, the rich soils around the Mediterranean?

The lack of vegetation, evapotranspiration and cloud albedo results in low rainfall and contributes to local and global warming.

Accelerating Soil erosion by Heavy equipment and Chemicals

Without appropriate action, California's Climate Change may lead to desertification and the collapse of it's huge agricultural complex (Walter Jehne)

Almost all farming-based cultures, from large civilizations to small peasant groups on little islands, have suffered from soil erosion. The erosion problems varied largely through time and space, and sometime extreme events have left a wide variety of imprints on the landscape over thousands of years. These are eroded hill-slopes and gullies, deposited sediments in sinks like lakes, foot-slopes, valleys, floodplains, river deltas and ocean floors. Many of them are of human origine and **the result of a lack of understanding, shortsightedness and poor land management.**

Markus Dotterweich has published an extensive study on this subject with over 400 scientific references in *Geomorphology* (2013), a peer reviewed scientific journal, under the title [The history of human-induced soil erosion: Geomorphic legacies, early descriptions and research, and the development of soil conservation – A global synopsis.](#)

Since we know the causes and the solutions, why do we continue making the same mistakes ?

Overview of eco-systems degraded by human activity

15-23% of the land is degraded by human activity

- More land was converted to cropland in the 30 years after 1950 than between 1700 and 1850
- 2 billion ha = size of the USA & China
- Annual Economic = USD 21-71 trillion/yr (in 2012, the Gross World Product: appr. US\$84.97 trillion)
- Private Sector is not involved

Geographical Distribution of Drylands

Figure 3.1 Geographical distribution of drylands, delimited based on the Aridity Index. The classification of the aridity index (AI) is: Humid $AI > 0.65$, Dry sub-humid $0.50 < AI < 0.65$, Semi-arid $0.20 < AI < 0.50$, Arid $0.05 < AI < 0.20$, Hyper-arid $AI < 0.05$. Data: TerraClimate precipitation and potential evapotranspiration (1980-2015) (Abatzoglou et al., 2018)

Appendix E

A World of Opportunity

October 2021

for Forest and Landscape Restoration 210 Million Hectares Pledged

An Urgent Need for Man-Nature Partnerships to restore our Blue Planet's damaged landscapes

The Great Work of Our Time. This image is from the Bonn Challenge, it is a global aspiration to restore 150 million hectares of the world's deforested and degraded lands by 2020. It was launched by world leaders at a ministerial roundtable in Bonn, Germany, in September 2011. Source: www.bonnchallenge.org/content/challenge, retrieved: 04-06-2015

Goal for 2030: 350 Million Hectares

FOREST AND LANDSCAPE RESTORATION OPPORTUNITIES

- Wide-scale restoration
- Mosaic restoration
- Remote restoration

OTHER AREAS

- Agricultural lands
- Recent tropical deforestation
- Urban areas
- Forest without restoration needs

The carbon sequestration capacity of fertile soils is enormous!

- Continuous grazing
- Chemical NPK fertilization
- Carbon sequestration < 20 tC/ha
- The loss of carbon is huge
- Poor water infiltration & retention

Soil regeneration

No spongy soil structure

20 m

- Regenerative grazing
- No chemical fertilizers
- No pesticides
- Carbon sequestration > 100 tC/ha
- 100 t/ha ≈ 1 Gt/100,000 km²
- ≈ 3.3x the size of Belgium
- Good water infiltration and retention

Soil carbon sponge

Photos D. Chassot December 1995
Very dry summer in Australia

Biodynamic pasture management with 500P

Vineyard soil - Rhone Delta, sandy clay loam (LAS)

Carbon sequestration and bio-fertility are 3D affairs

Depth of 70 cm

70 cm

Soil Analysis

Organic reference plot

1 year Biodynamics

Photo Pierre Masson (2014)

Appendix F - Sources of Inspiration

People and organizations healing damaged ecosystems

SEKEM, sustainable développement at its best

An Ecological, Cultural, Social, Economic and Agricultural Oasis in the Egyptian Desert

Having been started in 1977 on a 70 hectare stretch on the outskirts of Cairo in the midst of sand and desert by [Ibrahim Abouleish \(1937-2017\)](#), a Medical Doctor, Chemist and the recipient of the 2003 [Alternative Nobel Prize](#), **SEKEM** is unique in its kind and unites ecological, cultural, social, economic and agricultural development. Its success story where [biodynamic agriculture](#), soil health and desert greening play important roles, is unique in the World. It now has over a thousand employees and, in cooperation with almost 300 subcontracting farmers, cultivates close to 1700 hectares. SEKEM's schools which started more than 30 years ago and since 2009 include *Heliopolis University for Sustainable Development*, have a total enrollment of over 3000 children and youth. <https://www.facebook.com/sekemgroup>

A new concept that brings farmers, landowners, entrepreneurs, communities, nature, organisations and legislators together to transform degraded landscapes into thriving ecosystems and communities

Together with our partners we are committed to transforming 100 million ha of degraded land into thriving ecosystems and communities by 2040

PROJECTS IN
SOUTH AFRICA
AUSTRALIA
THE NETHERLANDS
SPAIN
INDIA
HAITI
ZAMBIA
GERMANY

Building a new balance between ecology, economics and hope

Brown's Ranch in North Dakota (<http://brownsranch.us/>)

Gabe Brown, a ND farmer, integrates regenerative grazing (mob grazing) with his crops in an area where annual rainfall is about 400 mm (16"). This highly productive and profitable system has allowed him to regenerate his soil at very low cost and to exceed the best grain yields of his neighbors.

Gabe Brown's Soil Health Principles

- **Limit disturbance:** Limit mechanical, chemical, and physical disturbance of soil.
- **Armour:** Keep soil covered at all times.
- **Diversity:** Maximum diversity of both plants and animal species.
- **Living roots:** Maintain living roots in the soil as long as possible throughout the years.
- **Integrate animals:** Nature does not function without animals

Dirt to Soil

One Family's Journey into Regenerative Agriculture

Gabe Brown

Bringing a run-down farm back to life

Polyface Farm in Virginia (<https://www.polyfacefarms.com>)

White Oak Pastures in Georgia

An initiative that has changed the lives of thousands of people and a whole region!

White Oak Pastures, 1000 ha farm - a Savary Global's showcase (hub)
Shift in the mid-1990s from a conventional farming system to holistic management according to the principles developed by Allan Savory

Vidéo - It's not the Cow, it's the How

The farmer's word: *Things that fascinated me when I was twenty were less fascinating at thirty, and were beginning to disgust me at forty.* (Will Harris)

<p>Before 1995: conventional management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 employees at minimum wage • Conventional breeding: cattle and pigs • Feed: conventional cereal-based feed laced with antibiotics and hormones • Meat quality: mediocre with pesticide, antibiotic and hormone residues • Economic situation: precarious - end of the road • Social situation: morose with a limited future in a poor and declining area of Georgia <p style="text-align: center; border: 2px solid red; padding: 5px; display: inline-block; color: red; font-weight: bold;">Unsustainable</p>	<p>After 20 years of holistic organic management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 165 well-paid employees • Diversified breeding: cattle, pigs, sheep, chickens, laying hens, turkeys, geese, ducks, rabbits... • Feeding : mainly via rotating pastures • Vegetable crops - biodiversity and soil carbon have soared! • Slaughterhouse and food processing on site • Product quality: excellent, wide choice • Economic situation: excellent - model for the future • Social situation: very positive, innovative company reviving a village (Bluffton) and a whole area of
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Chèvrerie and Cow - la Petite Brosse, a diversified French farm

TECHNIQUE Stratégie

200 allaitantes et 150 chèvres en système tout herbe

À la Chèvrerie and Cow, dans le Loiret, chèvres et vaches tournent en pâturage dynamique sur quelque 180 ha clôturés par près de 90 km de barrières.

LE CONTEXTE
 À Orléans, dans le Loiret, Jean-Baptiste et Stéphanie Drouin ont créé la Chèvrerie and Cow. Ils conduisent 200 black abersden-angus et 150 chèvres alpines, et se lancent cette année dans la production d'une saisonnière de porcs par an. Les trois ateliers sont en bio.
 L'exploitation accueille deux fois par semaine les clients dans un magasin à la ferme.
 180 ha, jusqu'alors cultivés, ont été implantés en herbe et divisés en paddocks pour un pâturage tournant dynamique.

D'herbe, de la luzerne, et c'est tout. C'est ainsi que Jean-Baptiste Drouin et sa femme Stéphanie, à Orléans, dans le Loiret, nourrissent 200 black abersden-angus et 150 chèvres alpines. Ce système tout herbe, ils ont dû le recréer de toutes pièces. Quand ils se sont installés, il y a eu dix ans d'années, aux exploitations du père de Jean-Baptiste, en pleine région céréalière, ils ont complètement revu l'assolement. Sur ces 180 ha regroupés autour de la ferme, tout était cultivé, se souvient Jean-Baptiste. Il n'y avait plus d'animaux. Mon père faisait des céréales, du maïs irrigué, mais ça n'était pas notre credo.

Dans un premier temps, ils constituaient un troupeau d'une soixantaine de chèvres, avec transformation et vente à la ferme. Ainsi naît la Chèvrerie and Cow avec l'arrivée du cheptel allaitant. Peut-être, toutes les parcelles sont retournées et implantées en prairie ou en luzerne. Ces surfaces sont aussi en partie plantées d'arbres fruitiers. Il nous a fallu plus de deux ans pour poser 30 km de clôtures, lance Jean-Baptiste. Côté matériel, il ne regrette rien. « Nous avions une moissonneuse-batteuse et cinq tracteurs, se souvient-il. Aujourd'hui, il n'en reste qu'un, et nous livisons à peine 200 t/an. Même pour déplacer les bovins, nous

n'attolons plus la bétailière. Nous les emmenons à cheval. Cela limite le stress des animaux. » Les 17 ha les plus proches de la ferme sont réservés aux chèvres. Elles sortent 3 h/jour, de mars à octobre, en pâturage tournant. « Il y a sept paddocks en tout, calcule Jean-Baptiste. Les chèvres laissent souvent des restes lorsqu'elles quittent une parcelle, j'y mets ensuite les cochons. Ils nettoient tout. »
« 24 heures par paddock »
 Même système de pâturage tournant dynamique pour les angus qui vivent occasionnellement dehors. Le troupeau, de 90 vaches et leurs sautes, tourne sur 150 ha, dont 100 sont divisés en petits paddocks, compte Jean-Baptiste. Nous avons tout éliminé, de sorte d'avoir des paddocks de 1 ha en moyenne, sur lesquels chaque lot ne reste pas plus de 24 h. » Dès que les mères et leurs veaux entendent à 4 h de l'élevage s'approcher du pré, tous livent le maïs pour se précipiter vers la sortie du champ. Jean-Baptiste

« With rotational grazing feeding the herds takes but a few seconds »

« Avec le pâturage tournant, nourrir les lots ne prend que quelques secondes »

Orléans. Le troupeau allaitant vient d'Écosse. En France, il n'a pas pu de l'herbe de la région.

Les animaux sont élevés par sexe, au service. Les mâles sont conservés pour la vente finale, et les femelles sont vendues comme reproductrices.

ouvre le paddock, et emmène son chien, un berger australien, derrière le troupeau. Les bovins ne se font pas prier, s'engouffrent dans la toundra fraîche et plongent la tête dans l'herbe fraîche. Voilà comment, en moins de trente secondes, le troupeau est tout un lot d'animaux », sourit-il. L'herbe, lorsque les sols sont moins portants, les animaux disposent d'une parcelle protégée par un bois. « Mais sous emménagement d'un ancien bâtiment en stabulation, pour des deux mois plus tard. » Les vaches sont groupées sur la sortie d'hiver et le début de printemps. Les vaches bénéficient ainsi d'une herbe abondante pour soutenir leur production laitière, et les éleveurs ne sont pas dépassés par la pousse. Les jeunes

sont serrés en fin d'année et élevés par sexe, éleveurs gèrent les mâles entiers pour la vente directe et un restaurateur, décrit Jean-Baptiste. Nous en abatons un par semaine. Les animaux sont âgés de 2 à 3 ans, et affichent en moyenne un poids de carcasse de 340 kg. Les parties à abattre de Cœur-sur-Loire (Nièvre), puis c'est un boucher qui s'occupe de la transformation, ajoute-t-il. Nous proposons des cois, de la viande au détail et des plats préparés de type pot-au-feu.

« Pas besoin de génisses »

Pour l'instant, aucune jeune femelle n'est conservée. Elles sont toutes vendues pour la reproduction, explique-t-il. Nous n'en avons pas encore besoin pour le renouvellement. La longévité de l'angus est telle qu'une vache peut avoir 12 à 15 veaux. Et il existe une forte demande en France pour ce type de génisses. Sans compter la tréscerie qu'elles représentent pour la ferme.

Cet hiver, la Chèvrerie and Cow a lancé un troisième atelier : du porc en plein air. Un petit bâtiment servait à ranger le matériel pour les cultures, précise Jean-Baptiste. Il y a construit des caissons paillés pour les cochons. Dehors, ils disposent de 2 ha divisés en paddocks. Avec seulement trois truies, Jean-Baptiste espère produire une soixantaine de porcelets par an. « Cela représente un animal à abattre par semaine, calcule-t-il. C'est tout ce dont j'ai besoin pour le magasin. » Cette réorientation vers l'élevage et un système extensif a considérablement réduit les charges de l'exploitation. « À 35 ans, je suis installé depuis six ans, et j'ai trois ans la ferme à ma place, mais j'ai emprunté en cours, souffle-t-il.

Hélène Chaligot

- Alimentation simple
- Autonomie alimentaire
- Maîtrise des prix de vente
- Travail autour des clôtures
- Surveillance rigoureuse de la pousse de l'herbe

GÉRER LE PÂTURAGE AVEC UN LOGICIEL

Pour l'aider dans son plan de gestion du pâturage, Jean-Baptiste Drouin travaille avec un logiciel. La méthode est répandue en Nouvelle-Zélande, où les éleveurs gèrent des centaines d'animaux sur des milliers d'hectares, et ne peuvent pas, par conséquent, se souvenir de l'état de chaque parcelle. Le logiciel retrace tout l'assolement. De son côté, le centre régulière-

ment les mesures de pouso de l'herbe, pour savoir où l'en sèmer et être au fait de chaque parcelle prête à recevoir un lot. C'est d'autant plus important en pâturage tournant.

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LA FRANCE AGRICOLE // 198 // 12 OCTOBRE 2018

Austrian CO₂ program - the Kaindorf initiative

In 2005 the Oekoregion Kaindorf, an Austrian association pursuing environmental and socio-economical goals, set up a CO₂ Program to reward farmers for their eco-systemic services. Organized on a private and voluntary basis the project is funded by companies concerned with their environmental impact seeking to offset the CO₂ emissions associated with their activities by purchasing CO₂ certificates from farmers. By participating in the program, farmers receive a payment of 30€ per ton of CO₂ sequestered in their soil over an agreed-on period.

Carbon Sequestration through Regenerative Agriculture

Gerhard Weisshäupl, an Austrian farmer who has been practicing Regenerative Agriculture for six years (GW in the photo), has increased humus levels by more than 0.5 points per year on his this plot enrolled in the Ökoregion Kaindorf carbon sequestration program (<https://www.oekoregion-kaindorf.at/index.php?id=167>).

(soil analysis based on GPS/RTK controlled sampling to a depth of 25 cm)

- Humus content in 2013 2.8%
- Humus content in 2017 5.4%
- Increase in humus content 2.6%
- CO₂ sequestration in 5 years 166 t
- Carbon sequestration in 5 years 46 t
- Cash payment per tonne CO₂ 30€
- Yearly cash payment approx. 1,000 €/ha

Management practices:

organic farming, minimum tillage, no-till, direct seeding, under-seeding, companion crops, agroforestry, compost, charcoal, diversified cover crops, "double cover crops", use of lactic acid inoculation, compost tea, etc.

Yearly carbon sequestration
 33 t/ha / CO₂ = 9 t/ha / C
 In comparison to the "4 per 1000" initiative
 ≈ 0,16 t/ha / based on soil with 1% C

Maïs grain population en bio
 Rendement 95 q/ha sans fertilisation
 Implanté après un couvert d'hiver - sous-semis trèfle blanc/ray-grass tardif lors du binage.
 En 5 ans d'Agriculture Régénérative, le taux d'humus de cette parcelle est passée de 3,4 à 5,8% (~+0,5%/an)

Companies concerned with their environmental impact finance the program by purchasing CO₂ certificates from farmers to compensate for the carbon emissions related to their business.

Farmers sequester carbon in their soil and receive a corresponding cash payments for this environmental service

Spectacular results from the very first year!

The Key Words :
HARVESTING WATER

Tiyeni
<https://www.tiyeni.org/>

@TiyeniFarming

Impact

25,000+

Farmers trained
in the DBF method
(Deep Bed Farmings)

Tiyeni is a Malawian initiative with a UK funding arm that shows farmers how to improve their soils and crops, using a set of "low tech - low input - low cost" agro-ecological methods that allow them to better manage water, soils, and crops. With little more than pickaxes and a little training, thousands of farmers and their families have dramatically improved their soils, their crops, their diets, and their lives.

Before

These Run-down Soils Led
to Endemic Famines,
Malnutrition and Poverty.

« The difference between
a Garden and a Desert
is not Water, it's Man »

Touareg Proverb

There is no Planet B, but there are lots of Plants to Cool it!

Partnering with Nature or taking the risky high-tech route: that is the question.

Partnering with Nature to re-green the planet:

based on the restoration of water and rain cycles, these low-tech systems require little energy, resources and investment. They are effective and pay for themselves after only a few years. Producing important benefits in terms of soil and landscape regeneration, food and water security, job creation and socio-economic development of many poor and arid regions of the South.

- Energy efficient
- Resource efficient
- Proven and safe practices
- Modest investments
- Fast payback (5 to 20 years)
- Quick results (3 to 7 years)
- Favorable socio-economic, ecological and energy footprint

South Africa Holistic management on the left has brought back biodiversity and natural fertility by regenerating the soil, greening the desert, restoring water cycles and cooling the

Zimbabwe : Thanks to regenerative grazing, the vegetation comes back to life, the climate becomes more balanced and some creeks start flowing again.

Pakistan: Planting one billion trees to regenerate a 3,500 km² area in 5 years! Has now been extended to 2028 and 10 billion

The High-Tech Route

- CCS technologies
- Solar geoengineering
- Food engineering

- Experimental
- Full of technical unknowns
- Highly energy, resource and capital intensive
- Expensive
- Timing: ????
- Financial sinkhole
- Uncertain results

High-Tech - High-Cost - High_Risk

A dive into the deep unknown!

Appendix F: We Need Thousands of Regeneration Projects all around the Planet to Tackle Climate Change, Food and Fresh Water Security, Poverty, Social Unrest, Migration, ...

Crucial sources of soil fertility, water and food security, these low-tech climate solutions allow for an immediate start of thousands of decentralized and autonomous greening projects all around the Globe.

- Simple and transparent organizational structures
- Produce fast and easily measurable results
- Low on capital
- Low-tech, low-input and low-energy
- High on environmental and climate benefits
- High on economic and social benefits
- High on people and community building

"Since water controls more than 95% of our planet's heat dynamics, our focus should be on water and the restoration of its cycles, not on CO₂ emissions!" - W.JEHNE